

Measuring quality of datasets using prediction explanation

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Abstract—Machine Learning (ML) techniques, especially Deep Neural Networks are achieving compelling results in many fields. However, the integration of ML solutions into critical systems where trustworthiness, reliability, and safety are crucial is an unsolved problem. The datasets have great importance for Machine Learning algorithms since the achievable precision during the training, and the accuracy of the final evaluation rely both on the quality and quantity of the data. Our goal was to improve the measurement of the quality of datasets. We recommend to 1) use the requirements gathered during systems design, and 2) generate metrics, which can provide information about the representativeness of a dataset to determine which are the problems that we can safely solve by using the data. This paper describes a general method for dataset evaluation using multiple measurement techniques, including prediction explanations. The method is demonstrated by applying it to a case study of categorising road signs.

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine Learning (ML) techniques are achieving great results in many fields, usually outperforms the traditional manually created algorithms. In general, the problem with these methods is that the increase of the accuracy most of the times means a decrease in the observability of the mechanism. The ML techniques as becoming more independent from hard-coded behaviours can reach better results. These methods are extracting their knowledge from datasets during a training period and later can use this knowledge to predict the outputs of previously unexplored inputs. In one perspective this way these techniques can learn more complex associations in the data than it would be possible in a manual way. However, they can handle only situations that relate somehow to the training datasets. We can improve the achieved results by using different ML techniques, but in the end, the dataset is a hard limit of the possible precision.

The motivation of the research is the significant role of the training and testing datasets in ML techniques. The training data determines the overall extractable knowledge, and the testing dataset is responsible for valid precision measurement. ML methods require a trust towards the quality of the dataset, especially if they are used in critical systems (e.g., automotive, transportation). When designing and verifying such systems, assurance of their compliance with the functional and safety requirements is mandatory, that needs to be thoroughly demonstrated. The ML method is used typically in one of the system components (e.g., processing sensor data), therefore it has to comply to the same requirements too. Determining the representativeness of the dataset for the entire task is a

complex problem. However, most of the datasets provide only essential diversity metrics like the number of elements or the precision of the labelling. These parameters are relevant but insufficiently detailed to establish a trust for in critical systems.

The goal of our research is to improve the measurements of the quality of the datasets. The primary purpose of a dataset is to represent a problem, a domain. The quality of the data means how accurate is this representation. Our idea is to provide a more detailed evaluation process based on 1) the given requirements of the problem, and 2) metrics obtained from various sources. We want to determine the use cases where it is safe to use the dataset and to find the missing, under and over represented scenarios.

We propose a method for improving the measurements of the quality of datasets. Our evaluation is based on the requirements representing the problem domain captured during traditional systems design. The evaluation method has three main parts: a general diversity, a static and dynamic analysis. The method contains metrics like standard numeric data about the structure of the dataset, summarised diversity metrics based on generic processing methods and using prediction explanations for more detailed analysis of the elements. The general method does not contain any domain-specific assumptions, but the metrics have to be mapped to the actual domain.

Gaining trust in ML techniques is hard but necessary to use them in real-world applications, especially in safety-critical systems [1]. The first step is to have metrics about the quality of the training and validation datasets. This paper summarises multiple existing quality measurement approaches (Sect. II) and proposes a general method for a more detailed dataset evaluation (Sect. III). We also demonstrate our method on a case study, highlighting how it can uncover problems in the quality of datasets (Sect. IV).

II. RELATED WORK

There are simple, essential numeric metrics about a dataset like the number of its elements, classes and size. However, richer ways were proposed to describe the collected data.

The ImageNet paper [2] describes an averaging method for evaluating the diversity. The idea is to stack all of the images from a selected class on top of each other and to generate a new image by calculating the mean value for every pixel. In theory, the created images should be completely grey, since ideally each of the pixels contained all of the colours. [2] We can identify some of the over-represented parts, and also can

compare the same classes from different datasets. Exporting the generated images as JPGs, we can associate the grey areas with the size of the files. The numeric representation of the metric is vital during evaluating large datasets.

It is difficult to determine the representativeness of a dataset alone accurately, but comparing multiple ones from the same domain can reveal some of the defects. Torralba and Efros [3] observed the biases in several datasets for general image classification. The main troubling idea is if we play a guessing game, where we randomly select an image from a dataset and trying to pick its source we can achieve too good results. The images are representing the same domain (the selected class) and collected similarly from the internet. However, the datasets have to have strong biases that allow us to identify them. Part of the cases we can trace back the source of these to the content of the images, like the age and environment of the cars. The authors also used a cross-evaluation for identifying the impact of these biases on the performance. The process using the subject dataset of the evaluation for the training and then running the tests on images from different datasets too, almost every time the results are the drop of the accuracy of the model on the other dataset compared to the original tests.

Prediction explanation [4] tools provide a glance inside the working mechanism of a black box model. They can calculate the relevance of the different parts of the input with one specific prediction. We can use the generated explanations also to examine the data, determine which features are well-, over- or under-represented. One of the most general approaches for prediction explanation is LIME [5]. It can interpret a prediction of a wide variety of ML techniques. It builds a linear model to approximate the examined method locally. The generated evaluations are detailed and precise, but generating them for a prediction is a computation-heavy, time-consuming task. Another method is Grad-CAM [6], which can interpret any CNN deep neural network. It has a more limited applicable field than LIME, but it is still quite extensive. It based on the sensitivity analysis of the layer, that represents the extracted features the most (for example the last convolutional layer of a convolutional network [6]). It can calculate de relevance of the input parameters based on the gradient values of the neurons. Its output explanation also less detailed than LIME's, but its main feature is that it does not have significant computational requirements, and gives very little overhead to the entire prediction process.

III. RECOMMENDED METHOD

Fig. 1 depicts how our approach combines systems engineering and ML engineering to improve the evaluation of the dataset's quality. The *Domain* is the collection of the scenarios that are part of the solvable problem. The possible inputs that can appear in an actual use-case are part of it. Even with a not too complex problem, we can get an enormous domain quite easily. It is not possible to use or collect the entire domain. Instead, a *Dataset* can represent the possible elements. Finding the right dataset for the actual problem is a difficult task, we can choose an existing one (or several ones) or can build it

from the ground. Regardless of which approach we use, the selected dataset must represent the domain well. To be able to evaluate this fact we must measure several parameters of the dataset. Usually, most of the dataset comes (or we can calculate it easily) with some *General diversity metrics*.

To improve the evaluation process, our first step starts from the *Requirements* representing the domain. In the *Static evaluation* step, these requirements are compared to the dataset. This step only uses the textual or graphical requirements and the plain dataset with some helper analysis (like well-defined image processing techniques). The *Dynamic evaluation* uses knowledge about the actual content of the elements in the dataset. We can estimate this knowledge with using the dataset in a simple *Model* with a *Prediction explanation* tool.

Fig. 1. Overview of the recommended method

General diversity measurements: As mentioned above these metrics usually come with the datasets, they are giving a minimal summary of the collected data. Typical examples are the number of elements, classes, sizes of the classes, distribution of the data points. Optionally they can reveal the source and method of the data collection, the used labelling technique. The purpose of these metrics is to provide a basic idea about the usability and quality of the dataset. In some cases, we can eliminate dataset candidates based on these numbers, but for final selection, we need more detailed evaluations [7].

Static evaluation: The functional and safety requirements provide a proper description of the scope of the problem. These requirements can have multiple formats and levels. Typical representations include textual (pattern-based), model-based (UML or SysML) and formal language based solutions [8]. The requirements can identify the relevant scenarios and also can determine if an element is part of or not part of the task. A dataset is a representation of the domain but giving an accuracy metric for the representation is a challenging problem. As a metric for this, we can evaluate the defined requirements on the dataset to verify its representativeness. The analysis method depends on the nature of the requirements and data. In general, in this step, we should find algorithmic methods that can generate features for the elements and the dataset which are usable for the evaluation of the requirements. For example, for analysing image data, we usually can use aggregated metrics based on the pixel values or some edge detection algorithms.

Dynamic evaluation: In this step, we run an example model to extract further parameters of the dataset with the help of a prediction explanation tool [4]. This tool can identify the relevant and irrelevant parts of the input data, which can be used for further analysis. These can help the evaluation of the requirements by the categorisation of the input features by relevance. The generated importance maps also can define relevance patterns inside the dataset. For example, if an input parameter is never used for the prediction, it can indicate that it is not relevant for the problem or not represented well, i.e., there are not enough example for the possible scenarios.

The dynamic evaluation can contain cross-evaluation between multiple datasets. Since the datasets represent the same domain, we expect that we should get similar results with the tests, independently from the datasets that are used for the training. Thus we can train multiple models (but with the same architecture) on multiple datasets and after that, and we can evaluate the trained models on each other's test data [3].

IV. CASE STUDY

We created a case study to demonstrate the working mechanism of the method and to show an example solution that can work with almost any image classification problem.

Solvable problem: The task is to categorise the road signs in Belgium¹ and Germany². Although there are several minor differences in the legislation of the countries, in this case study we assume they are the same domain (we can only use the road signs which are the same in the two countries from the datasets for the evaluation methods that requires comparisons). The following requirements can define the domain and the tasks of a hypothetical system that can use ML techniques (the requirements of such existing systems are not public).

REQ1 The system shall identify the road sign in Belgium or Germany. The classification shall handle all of the possible sign types. However, finding the image parts which are containing a sign is a task for another system in the pipeline, this system only responsible for the categorisation of the signs.

REQ2 The system shall handle images with different lighting conditions, such as dark, half-light, daylight, harsh sunlight, shadows.

REQ3 The system shall perform the classification independently from the environment of the sign, such as buildings, countryside, trees, sky, street.

REQ4 The system shall identify the traffic signs from different angles, and image quality too.

REQ5 The system shall identify the traffic signs even when they are partly covered.

Note that our goal is to demonstrate the recommended method, but a real scenario would require more detailed refinements of these high-level requirements.

General diversity measurements: The German dataset is almost ten times larger than the Belgian and has a more

reasonable size. Some of the classes in the Belgian dataset only contains around twenty images which are not enough data in most of the cases.

Dataset	Classes	Training	Tests
Belgian	62	4575	2520
German	43	39209	12569

TABLE I
GENERAL DIVERSITY OF THE DATASETS

As a general diversity metric, we can evaluate the averaging image technique [2]. In the following figures, the leftmost image is generated by stacking and averaging all of the images in the given class. The stacked image should have a greyish background if the class has enough diversity since this colour is the result of mixing all the others.

Fig. 2. Stop and Cattle crossing sign stacked and example images (Belgian)

For example, the stacked image of the cattle crossing sign has a green background (Fig. 2), which indicates that most of the images were taken in a green environment. The problem is that these signs not necessary has a green background (winter or blue sky). However, with these images, it is a possibility that the ML technique learns the background too.

Static evaluation: REQ1: The datasets only contain images of road signs, they can be used to categorise signs, but not to detect them. The first problem with both of the datasets is that they do not contain all of the road sign categories. There are around 150 road sign types [9], but the Belgian dataset contains 63, the missing elements mostly highway, roadwork and train related signs. The German dataset is less complete, there are 43 classes, and 8 of them are just different speed limits; crosswalk or parking signs are entirely missing.

REQ2: We can estimate the lighting conditions from the overall brightness of the pictures which can be determined by calculating the mean pixel value on the images. The diversity of the lighting conditions is eligible in both of the datasets.

Fig. 3. RGB values in the STOP sign category in the Belgian dataset

REQ3: We can examine the diversity of the images with calculating mean RGB values for the images (Fig.3). Mostly the reds are dominating the pictures, but this is natural because of the red parts of the signs. The differences between the

¹Belgium Traffic Sign Dataset: <https://btsd.ethz.ch/shareddata/>

²German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark: <http://benchmark.ini.rub.de/>

distribution of the RGB values can indicate the different environments on the images.

REQ4 and REQ5: The stacked images almost clearly show the signs in the centre of the images, which indicates that there aren't too many images that contain only parts of the signs or partly covered ones. Also, we want to see a grey colour in the background, but some of the classes have a coloured background (mainly those that contain fewer examples).

Dynamic evaluation: This evaluation requires an actual running model on the dataset. Our choice is a simple convolutional deep neural network [10]. It contains three convolutional layers for the feature extraction and another three fully connected layers for the classification. The input size of the network is 32 by 32 as the rescaled images in the datasets.

We trained two models with the same (above described) architecture on the training part of the two datasets. Both of the training was only 80 epochs, at this point we have managed to get decent enough results for the evaluation. First, we run the inference with the datasets' test data and then used the other's tests.

Train / Test	Belgian	German	Bg. STOP	Gm. STOP
Belgian	68.3%	26.8%	35.6%	12.5%
German	78.4%	94.2%	84.4%	95.4%

TABLE II

THE RESULTS OF THE CROSS-EVALUATIONS OF THE MODELS

In general, the model with the Belgian dataset has weaker performance results, and its accuracy dropped more with the tests from the other dataset than the one trained with the German data. However, the German model loses 6% in accuracy too, which is significant if we calculate that the training contained more than ten times more images than the Belgian dataset (for example there are 50 STOP signs in the Belgian and 800 in the German dataset). The first part of the table contains the results of the evaluation of the entire test sets of the datasets and second half is an example for the STOP sign category. With ideal conditions, the differences should be far less between a class and the entire results, but we used a simple model with a short training on unbalanced datasets.

Grad-CAM can provide prediction explanation for any convolutional network so that it can interpret our model's predictions too. It generates the relevance maps for the inputs, to help the further evaluation processes, there is an image with the raw greyscaled mask and another with the coloured heatmap on the top of the input image.

The prediction explanation can help the evaluation by highlighting the main parts of the images. These parts are relevant for the predictions we want them to be diverse enough.

The grey-scaled images are the raw relevance masks, which are more usable with algorithms to recognise patterns (for example selecting the images with less white areas from the entire dataset). The coloured heatmaps on top of the original images are more usable for manual evaluation. The whites and reds are the most relevant areas. As the first example shows too, most of the signs are clear and in the centre. The second example is more complicated (it shows a partly covered

sign) than the more general first. These scenarios are harder to handle, it is essential to have enough data from these. In both of the datasets, the scenarios with the partly covered sign are under-represented. The generated masks also can help the static evaluation for selecting the subject on the images.

Fig. 4. Example for the dynamic evaluation (Belgian)

Summary: the evaluation process generated valuable, usable metrics, managed to cover all of the requirements at least by one measurement. However, we discovered some severe deficiencies with both of the datasets, which eliminates the possible use of them for the defined recognition task. Also, our method identified several possible improvements of the datasets to be complete and usable.

V. CONCLUSION

We managed to generate a meaningful evaluation for the case study based on the proposed general method. The requirement analysis part of the process and selecting the relevant evaluation methods for checking the rules with almost every system needs some level of manual work. However, we can automate most of the evaluations independently from any domain. Overall our approach even if it requires further specifications of the evaluation methods can be used efficiently for gaining more trust towards ML techniques applicability in critical systems.

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